

Statistical Process Control for Monitoring and Reducing Variation in Analytical Measurement

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ABSTRACT

Aim : An extremely important issue in quality management is monitoring and diagnosing processes, and, subsequently, supervising them using so-called control charts. **Background :** Classical scheduling theory takes a narrow, static view of performance. In reality the assessment of scheduling performance is a particularly difficult task. In typical production processes, charts with constant parameters are commonly used, such as x-R, x-s, CUSUM, EWMA and others, which, in most cases, are effective tools for process stability evaluation. Charts considered untypical (in statistical process control) are those with variable sample sizes, variable sampling intervals and/or variable control limits. Such charts are used when process analysis based on standard, well-known charts may lead to serious errors. **Objective :** Modern control charts are a response to the requirements of Industry and are an excellent tool for supervising production processes. Their use together with Cp and Cpk indices and other process capability indices is a starting point for process improvement. **Method and Results :** The methodology of preparation of nonstandard charts is inadequately recognized and rarely used in practice. **Conclusion:** The theory of their design and examples of their use will be presented and characterized in this paper.

Keywords: statistical process control (SPC), control charts.

INTRODUCTION

Meclizine HCl 1-[(4-chlorophenyl)phenyl)methyl]-4-[(3-methylphenyl)methyl]piperazine. It is an Antiemetic Agent anti- histamine agent. through its antagonistic action on the H1 receptors, meclizine primarily works by inhibiting signaling pathway transduction through histaminergic neurotransmission from the vestibular nuclei and nucleus of the solitary tract (NTS) to the chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ) and medullary vomiting center. Meclizine may also decrease the labyrinth excitability and vestibular stimulation. Most histamine H1 antagonists are reported to be readily absorbed following oral administration. Upon oral administration, the time to reach peak plasma concentrations (C_{max}) of meclizine is about 3 hours post-dose, with the value ranging from 1.5 to 6 hours.

Meclizine is excreted in the urine as metabolites and in the feces as unchanged drug

Fig 1: Structure of Meclizine HCl

The process of demonstrating that an analytical method is accurate and is suitable is known as method validation. Efficiency of an analytical method is defined by the simplicity of validation procedure. A strategy needs to be developed for quick testing of

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commercial samples, prototypes and preclinical study samples. The information obtained during technique development and validation is useful in method designing and future improvement.¹ Over time significant variations in measurements can be observed, major reasons being contaminated chemical reagents, solvents and environmental factors.

A very important aspect in the area of SPC is technological process stability and process capability analysis, as well as process supervision (monitoring, diagnosing and regulation) with control charts and capability indices. These very convenient tools are widely used today; nevertheless, when selecting a particular chart or factor type, many errors are made. Nowadays, it is not enough to use the simplest chart types. Technological process capability and very high process accuracy often demand the use of more sophisticated tools, such as new-generation control charts or dynamic charts (adaptive charts). They take into account variable process conditions and adapt to them by changing collected sample sizes, sampling periods or control limit locations. Measurement data from a manufacturing process are shown in a control chart, typically in the form of low quantity samples plotted against time, with the general mean value of the data displayed on the central line. Not only that, but lines are plotted using a region where their natural processes differ from one another. Plotted at a distance of $\pm 3s$ (three sample mean values of the standard deviation) from the central line. Results from a statistically controlled, stable process remain inside the control bounds. A signal arises when an observation value appears outside of the self-variability area, or stability area. It is also a signal if observation values group in one of a few specific configurations, although none of the values are beyond the stability area (this is called a serial out-of-control signal). The appearance of a process out-of-control signal forces the process owner to take preventive and corrective measures.

1.1 Statistical Process Control

Statistical process control (SPC) is a powerful collection of problem-solving tools useful in achieving process stability and improving capability through the reduction of variability. SPC is one of the greatest technological developments of the twentieth century because it is based on sound underlying

principles, is easy to use, has significant impact, and can be applied to any process.

Its seven major tools are^{2,3}:

1. Histogram or stem-and-leaf plot
2. Check sheet
3. Pareto chart
4. Cause-and-effect diagram
5. Defect concentration diagram
6. Scatter diagram
7. Control chart

1.2 Statistical analysis of data:

Statistics is a compilation of mathematical techniques or plans for gathering, characterizing, arranging, and evaluating numerical data. Since studies frequently produce such quantitative data, statistics is an essential tool for measurement and research. Researchers employ statistics for purposes beyond simple data manipulation; statistical methods originate from the main objectives of study. Inferential statistical analysis and descriptive statistical analysis are the two uses of statistical data that can be made in educational research. Statistical analysis of data can be done by descriptive statistical analysis, inferential statistical analysis, describing the variation of data, numerical summary of data (measuring central tendency, mean, median, mode, central dispersion measurement, range, variance, standard deviation), graphical tools such as histogram, box plot, scatter plot, run chart.

The main aim of this study is to monitor and reduce the variation in the analytical method of instruments (i.e., UV-Vis Spectrophotometer and HPLC) by the use of Statistical Process Control (SPC) method.

- Descriptive statistical analysis
- Inferential statistical analysis
- Describing variation of data
- Numerical summary of data
- Measures of central tendency

A statistical analysis of the observed values of a continuous variable that considers the distribution's center is known as central tendency. The three points that are related to the center are the mean, median, and mode. Central tendency measures can be applied to ordinal, interval, or ratio scales. Continuous variables

are used in many inferential statistical tests, and they are all dependent on the central tendency of the corresponding sample data.

Mean:

Often referred to as Average. The mean of a sizable group of people is referred to as the population mean. The mean of a subset of data taken from a larger population or activity is called the sample mean. The average is another name for the sample mean. By adding together all of the data and dividing by the total number of observations, one can determine the weighted center point of a distribution.

$$\bar{X} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

The sample mean will be represented by the character \bar{X} (x-bar). The observed values of a specific variable are all denoted by the same letter (typically x), and each individual value is denoted by a subscript number or letter. For instance, x_i denotes the i th observation in a set of data. The symbol sigma (Σ) represents the sum (addition) of all variable observations. The formula for this equation, often known as the arithmetic mean, is as follows:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

In this equation, all observations (x_i) for variable x are added together from the first ($i = 1$) to the last (n) observation and divided by the total number of sample observations (n).

Median:

Any score distribution's center is the sample median. The figure below which 50% of all scores are found is indicated. The distribution is divided into two equal parts (the 50th percentile) by the median, which is derived from the Latin word medianus, which meaning "middle".

As an illustration, consider the following numbers: 1, 2, 2, 3, 3, 4, 4, 4, 5, 6, 6, 6, 7, 7, 8, 8. There are 23 observations in this case, as in the previous example. The value that precisely lies in the middle of the distribution in this case is the median, or 5. The

median is the average of the two center scores, and the 50th percentile is situated between them if the number of observations is even.

Mode:

Sample mode is also known as popular value in continuous distribution of scores. For example: 2, 6, 7, 5, 3, 8, 7, 6, 5, 3, 2, 5, 4, 6, 8, 3, 4, 4, 7, 6, 5, 1, 5

The modal value in the above distribution of observations is 5 since it has the highest frequency. The mode is the simplest, but least useful measure of the center for a distribution. The mode is most useful when continuous data has been divided into categories (e.g., a histogram) or where it represents the category with the greatest frequency.

Measures of Central Dispersion:

Measure of central dispersion is opposite of measure of central tendency. Range, variance and standard deviation are three measures of dispersion. "R" is the difference between highest and lowest value in set of outcomes.

R = highest observation - lowest observation

Variance:

It measures the variability in sample data. It is total of squared deviations from sample average for each observation divided by sample size minus one.

$$s^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}$$

Standard Deviation:

Square root of variance is defined as standard deviation or SD. It also measures variability in mean values and is used to express dispersion.

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}}$$

Standard deviation is expressed in same unit as the data obtained such as temperature if denoted by °C will be displayed as the same unit in Standard deviation results.

Hypothesis tests:

The hypothesis tests are intended to verify if the experimental data are consistent with certain theoretical hypothesis.

- The null hypothesis symbolized by H_0 considers that the two elements or series of elements are equal.
- The second step consists in measuring the deviation between different characteristics.
- The third step is to calculate the probability P to have this deviation if H_0 is true.

Graphical tools:

Are used to visually explain the data. Example: Histogram, Box plot, scatter plot and run chart.

Control charts:

Shewhart's genius lay in offering process operators a straightforward yet powerful visual aid to help them decide on process behavior in real time. Shewhart therefore created the control chart, a very straightforward statistical tool, to help discern between variation with common and unique causes. A time-ordered graph with action limit lines drawn around the historical average of the sub-grouped data for a process is called a control chart. Any data points found outside of the action limits are highly unlikely to be the result of chance because of the way the lines are calculated. Control charts are analytical tools that, by comparing the actual distribution patterns of result data with standardised distribution patterns obtained from probability statistics, allow a visual difference between random fluctuation or "noise" in a process and substantial change. Control charts provide a clear advantage over conventional statistical analysis techniques since they show changes in outcome measures over time.

Application of Statistical Process Control Method:

- Data Collection
- Data is collected by performing Analysis on the Developed Method of the Instruments.

- Determine the Mean, Standard Deviation, Variance, Highest Value and Lowest Value

- Plot the Scatter Diagram and the Histogram by using the collected data.

- Check if the Data collected is Normally Distributed by Q-Q Probability Plot.

- Set the Sample size (n) and Set the UCL and LCL for the Control Chart

- Collect the data by performing analysis, taking Sample size (n) at regular time intervals.

- Calculate Mean of each Subgroups.

- Construct the Control Chart (i.e., X-bar, R Chart)

- Calculate the Average Run Length

- Interpret the Control Charts

- Calculate the Process Capability Indices (PCIs) (i.e., C_{pm} and C_{pk})

Methods:**1. Data collection:**

1 ml of standard solution of diluted to 10 ml with 0.2% v/v triethylamine water and pH adjusted to 3 using orthophosphoric acid. All above solutions filtered and injected in system. Chromatogram for 25 samples was recorded and area of chromatogram was taken as data of peak area.

2. Using Excel to create descriptive statistics table:

Chromatogram peak area of 25 samples inserted in word and data in analyzed using statistics selecting the input range as 25 and selecting any cell as output range. Check confidence level for mean, Kth largest and Kth smallest.

3. Constructing histogram and scatter diagram:

Determining the first stage in histogram is number of class and calculating the square root of the total number of samples i.e., square root of "N". next is selection of class width by dividing range of data set with number of classes by subtracting lowest and

highest point from range. And then we need to “bin” the values to construct histogram in excel. This will be the first bin value and then class width values should be successively added up to the number of class. Then construct scatter diagram using the histogram data and obtain a scatter chart.

4. Chi square goodness of fit test:

According to null hypothesis H₀ is chromatogram peak area and shows normal distribution and alternative hypothesis H₁ does not show normal distribution. Test is done in excel, first step is selecting upper- and lower-class interval and for that class width is calculated then range of data is divided by number of classes. Then the smallest value of data point is lower limit class and for upper class limit add class width to lower class value. Here we select 7 as number of classes. to get the class interval of 7 add class width to lower class interval, getting the upper- and lower-class intervals. Then expected probability is calculated by “=NORM.DIST

(x, mean, standard_dev, cumulative) NORM.DIST(x, mean, standard_dev, cumulative)” formula. Here the first x is upper class interval and other x is lower interval value. For mean and standard deviation, the calculated value of mean and standard deviation from descriptive studies of 50 samples is put. For cumulative value, 1 is entered. Then the expected frequency is calculated in next column by multiplying expected probability by total number of samples i.e., N=50 in next column insert observed frequency and select 7 cells and insert “=FREQUENCY (B2:B51,D53:D59)”. In the brackets of the formula select absorbance data and upper-class interval and click ENTER. Then “Chi Square Values” column is constructed by taking square of “Expected Frequency” minus “Observed Frequency” divided by “Expected Frequency” and sum of chi square values is taken as calculated chi square value. In next step calculate p value by “=CHISQ.DIST.RT (x,deg_freedom)”. In place of “x” insert Calculated Chi Square value and in place of “deg_freedom” insert 6. The degree of freedom is number of classes minus one.

The Calculated Chi Square value is compared with the “Critical Chi Square” value.

5. Constructing normal Q-Q plot:

Arrange the data set under the heading “Area” in ascending order by using “Sort & Filter group” on the data tab in Excel and in the adjacent column, give numbers 1, 2, 3, Up to 25, under column heading “Rank”. Next step is to calculate the “Percentile” values of the “Rank”. To calculate enter “=(B2-0.5)/25” formula in the first cell. Press Enter. Select the first cell and drag it up to the last cell to apply this formula in all of the remaining cell then calculate the z score based on the percentile values i.e., “Normal Theoretical Quantiles”. Enter “=NORM.S.INV(C2)” formula. Press Enter. Select the first cell and drag it up to the last cell to apply this formula in all of the remaining cell. Z score, based on the original data (Area values) and "Data Quantiles," is the last step in the calculation process. Enter the formula “=STANDARDIZE(x, mean, standard deviation)”. For "x," choose the first cell in the "Area" column. For "mean," substitute the absorbance data's mean value. For "table," substitute the standard deviation value from the previously prepared "descriptive statistics" table.

6. Setting the Sample size (n) and Sampling Frequency:

For HPLC Method, Sample size selected is 1 i.e., data is collected individually. Sample is run every 1 hour in a day.

7. Setting the Control Limits for I-Chart and MR-Chart:

Moving range is calculated in excel by calculating moving range as \overline{MR} by formula $\overline{MR}_i = |x_i - x_{i-1}|$.

7.1 Individual Chart (I-Chart)

In the I-Chart, warning limits for both the UCL and LCL are calculated using a 2 standard deviation (2σ) difference from the Center Line (CL).

7.2 Moving range (MR) chart:

In the MR-Chart, warning limit is calculated using a 2 standard deviation (2σ) difference from above the Center Line (CL).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

1. Descriptive statistics of Meclizine

Methanol was selected as a solvent and Phosphate buffer pH 3 was selected to make up the volume. 230.7 nm was selected as the working wavelength. From Table 1 of Meclizine Absorbance data, there is not much difference between “Mean”, “Median” and “Mode” of the Absorbance This gives the rough estimation that the data is Normally Distributed. The Kurtosis value was found to be 2.05 which lies almost in the -2.0 to +2.0 range which indicates the normal distribution of data. The Skewness value is -0.63 which is very close to zero, hence we can conclude that the data follows normal distribution. The Confidence Interval at the 95% Confidence Level was found to be 0.33206 ± 0.0025 .

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of Meclizine 10 ppm absorbance data N=25

Area	
Mean	446901.44
Standard Error	1050.627741
Median	445259
Mode	#N/A
Standard Deviation	5253.138705
Sample Variance	27595466.26
Kurtosis	-0.858224621
Skewness	0.587748674
Range	16238
Minimum	440212
Maximum	456450
Sum	11172536
Count	25
Largest(1)	456450
Smallest(1)	440212
Confidence Level(95.0%)	2168.389084

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of Meclizine 10 ppm absorbance data N=50

Meclizine 10ppm Absorbance	
Mean	0.33206
Standard Error	0.001266656
Median	0.333
Mode	0.333
Standard Deviation	0.008956607
Sample Variance	8.02208E-05
Kurtosis	2.055647433

Skewness	-0.632410719
Range	0.051
Minimum	0.302
Maximum	0.353
Sum	16.603
Count	50
Largest(1)	0.353
Smallest(1)	0.302
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.00254544

From the histogram it was observed that sample follows a roughly normal distribution and there is no correlation in absorbance data of Meclizine HCl i.e., there is no trend in data and data points are randomly distributed.

2. Histogram and Scatter Diagram:

Fig 2: Histogram of Absorbance of Meclizine HCl 10ppm at 230.7nm

Fig 3: Scatter Plot of Absorbance of Meclizine HCl 10ppm at 230.7nm

From the Histogram, we can conclude that the absorbance data of Meclizine HCl roughly follows Normal Distribution. From the Scatter Plot, we can

conclude that there is no correlation in the absorbance data of Meclizine HCl i.e., there is no trend in the data and the data points are randomly distributed.

The Test Chi Square is less than the Critical Chi Square i.e., $\chi^2 < \chi^2$ and the P-value is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$). Therefore, we do not reject the Null Hypothesis. Hence, we can conclude that the absorbance data shows Normal Distribution.

3. Chi Square Goodness of Fit Test

Table no: 3 Chi Square Goodness of Fit Test for Peak Area data of Meclizine HCl (N=25)

Sr. No.	Lower Class Interval	Upper Class Interval	Expected Probability	Expected Frequency	Observed Frequency	Observed Chi Square
1	440212	442918.3333	0.224155552	5.60388881	7	0.347816761
2	442918.3333	445624.6667	0.179827929	4.495698231	6	0.503353138
3	445624.6667	448331	0.203257197	5.081429917	3	0.852584916
4	448331	451037.3333	0.177211603	4.430290075	3	0.461759764
5	451037.3333	453743.6667	0.119175399	2.979384968	1	1.31502471
6	453743.6667	456450	0.061816299	1.545407472	4	3.898664004

Table 4: Chi Square Goodness of Fit Test for Absorbance data of Meclizine HCl (N=50)

Sr. No.	Lower Class Interval	Upper Class Interval	Expected Probability	Expected Frequency	Observed Frequency	Chi Square
1	0.302	0.309	0.005017288	0.250864384	1	2.237081888
2	0.309	0.316	0.031462008	1.573100396	1	0.208787732
3	0.316	0.323	0.119398837	5.969941867	3	1.477494236
4	0.323	0.33	0.253168607	12.65843033	14	0.14218265
5	0.33	0.337	0.300324266	15.01621332	21	2.384469523
6	0.337	0.344	0.199378522	9.968926109	5	2.476718797
7	0.344	0.351	0.074020149	3.701007474	4	0.024154647

4. Normal Q-Q Plot:

Fig 4: Normal Q-Q Plot of N=50 Meclizine 10ppm Sample at 230.7nm

The points lie on the 45 degree reference line, it leads to a conclusion that the absorbance data is normally distributed.

5. Mean and Range of each Subgroups:

The Grand Mean of Range was found to be 0.0118.

6. Control Limits for X-bar Chart

Fig 5: X-Bar Chart of Meclizine HCl Absorbance of 22 Samples (n=5)

X-bar Chart Upper Control Limit:

For upper control limits for X-bar chart UCL was found to be 0.3377.

X-bar Chart Lower Control Limit:

For lower control limits for X- bar chart LCL was found to be 0.3241.

7. Control Limits for R-Chart

Fig 6: R Chart of Meclizine HCl Absorbance of 22 Samples (n=5)

R-Chart Upper Control Limit:

For R- chart upper control limit, UCL was found to be 0.0250 and

R-Chart Lower Control Limit:

For R- chart lower control limit, LCL was taken as 0. X- bar chart shows that The application of decision rules for detecting non-random patterns on control charts indicates that, in this situation, the method is in statistical control. In R chart sample number 3 is above the upper control limit which indicated the process variability is out of the control limits at that specific sample point, it is an indication of assignable cause of variation. According to Table 5:

Table 5: Calculated PCIs values of UV method

PCIs	Values	Comment
C_p	1.0003	Capable
C_{pk}	1.0003	Capable
C_{pk}	1.0003	Capable
C_{pm}	0.89	Not Capable

In process capability indices (PCIs) the C_{pk} (lower) was found to be 1.0003 and C_{pk} (upper) was found to be 1.0003 and C_{pm} was found to be 0.89. UV Spectrophotometric method of Meclizine HCl is Capable of producing the results within statistical

control. But, C_{pm} value is not within the acceptable limits. Therefore, the analytical method is not capable of producing results on target values for long period of time.

For HPLC Statistical data is collected in form of Peak area in chromatogram and 25 number of samples were run. From the Histogram that the Chromatogram Peak Area data for Meclizine HCl closely follows the Normal Distribution. The Scatter Plot shows that there is no correlation in the Peak Area data of Meclizine HCl, indicating that there is no trend in the data and that the data points are randomly distributed. For Chi Square Goodness of Fit Test it was concluded that The Test Chi Square is less than the Critical Chi Square i.e., $\chi^2 < \chi^2_{crit}$ and the P-value is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$). Therefore, we do not reject the Null Hypothesis. We can conclude from Normal Q-Q plot that the Peak Area of Meclizine HCl data shows Normal Distribution. The observation leads to the conclusion that the absorbance data is normally distributed. For upper control limit UCL found to be 463258.82 and for lower control limits LCL found to be 430544.06. For moving range chart UCL found to be 20093 and LCL taken as 0.

8. Control charts interpretation:

The I-Chart shows that all plotted values fall within the control limits and also within the warning limits therefore, the HPLC method of Meclizine HCl is in statistical control. In addition, there is no evidence of cyclical or periodic behaviour in the Individual Control Chart. The application of decision rules for detecting nonrandom patterns on control charts indicates that, in this situation, the method is in statistical control. In the MR-Chart all the plotted points fall within the control limits. However, two points i.e., sample number 12 and 13 lies above the warning limits. Some preventive actions should be taken (such as checking column temperature, handling solvents with more efficiency, etc.) to bring the HPLC method towards more stable process. Since, all the plotted points falls within the control limits and the use of decision rules to identify non-random patterns on control charts demonstrates that the HPLC method is in statistical control.

PCI values were found as:

Table 6: Calculated PCIs values for Meclizine Hcl HPLC method

PCIs	Values	Inferences
C_p	1.038	Capable
C_{pkl}	1.038	Capable
C_{pku}	1.038	Capable
C_{pm}	1.004	Capable

The values of the C_p and C_{pk} (i.e., C_{pkl} and C_{pku}) falls in the acceptable limits as shown in the table. Hence, the HPLC method of Meclizine HCl is Capable of producing the results within statistical control. Also, C_{pm} value is within the acceptable limits. Therefore, the HPLC method is capable of producing results on target values for long period of time.

CONCLUSION:

The Statistical Process Control method by the use Control Charts is most widely in used in the manufacturing industries (for e.g., Pharmaceutical Industries). The procedure of Analytical Method for a specific Analytical Instruments (for e.g., UV Spectrophotometer and HPLC Instrument) is same in analogy as the Manufacturing process. Hence, SPC method in the form of Control Charts can be used for controlling Analytical Method process

The UV Spectroscopic Method of Meclizine was developed and validated successfully as per the ICH Q2R1 guidelines. After validation of UV Method, the SPC method by the use of Control Charts viz. X-bar Chart and Range Chart was performed. The absorbance data shows normal distribution since, it is concluded by the use of Histogram, Chi Square Goodness of Fit Test and Normal Q-Q Plot. The X-bar chart of absorbance data of sample size 5 shows only one data point touching the upper control limit. There is no evidence of non-random patterns in the x-bar control chart as per the non-random pattern decision rules. In case of R- chart of absorbance data, the data point sample no. 3 is above the upper control limit. Therefore, the process variability is not in control. Hence, some corrective actions should be taken in order to reduce variability. However, no non-random is observed in R-Chart. Therefore, by observing X-bar and R-Chart together, it is concluded that the UV Method of Meclizine HCl is in statistical

control. The Process Capability Study is conducted by calculating PCIs viz. C_p , C_{pk} and C_{pm} . The calculated PCIs values lies in 1 to 1.33. Therefore, it is concluded that the UV Method of Meclizine HCl is capable of producing the results in statistical control.

The SPC Method using Control Charts viz. Individual Chart (I-Chart) and Moving Range Chart (MR-Chart) was carried out. The Histogram, Chi Square Goodness of Fit Test, and Normal Q-Q Plot all indicate that the absorbance data³ exhibits a normal distribution. The HPLC method of meclizine HCl is in statistical control because the I-Chart demonstrates that all plotted values fall within both the control and warning ranges. Additionally, the Individual Control Chart shows no signs of cyclical or periodic behaviour. The use of decision rules to identify non-random patterns on control charts demonstrates that the procedure is in statistical control in this instance. All of the plotted points in the MR-Chart are inside the control limits. But two points, namely sample no. 12 and 13, are over the alert levels. To make the HPLC technique a more stable process, some preventive measures should be implemented (such as checking the column temperature, handling solvents more effectively, etc.). The HPLC process is in statistical control because all of the plotted points fall within the control limits and because non-random patterns on control charts can be recognised using decision rules.

Declaration

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Ethical Statement

Authors are required to disclose financial or non-financial interests that are directly or indirectly related to the work submitted for publication.

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